

dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : The dopamine D2 receptor (also known as D₂R), encoded by DRD2, is the main receptor for most antipsychotic drugs. Optimal dopamine levels favor D₁R cognitive stabilization, and D₂R levels devise the cognitive flexibility in humans. Its structure in complex with the antipsychotic risperidone (used to treat schizophrenia) has been determined and cases like schizophrenia are caused by disordering in equilibration of D₂R states which leads to problems in signal transferring between the nervous systems. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of DRD2, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

^{*}ML dicoveries of DRD2 synergy in Meningiomas

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Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Meningioma	2
1.1.1 World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2 Historical perspective	3
1.1.3 Pathophysiology	4
1.2 dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2)	4
1.3 Insight behind the work	6
1.4 Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	7
2 Methods	7
2.1 Static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.2 Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	7
2.3 Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	8
2.4 Regarding biological insight	9
3 Results & Discussion	9
3.1 DRD2 related synergies	9
3.1.1 DRD2 - individual genes	9
4 Conclusion	14
5 References	16

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2)

Seeman [13] and Creese et al. [14], in their reviews study the classification of Dopamine receptors which are divided into D1 and D2 subtypes on the basis of their pharmacological and biochemical characteristics.

Cote et al. [15] stimulated the D-2 dopamine receptor in the intermediate lobe (IL) of the rat pituitary gland to find that it diminishes both basal and isoproterenol-stimulated adenylate cyclase activity. Using cholera toxin-treated IL tissue as a useful experimental system to investigate the involvement of guanyl nucleotides in the func-

tioning of the IL D-2 dopamine receptor, they hypothesized that the D-2 dopamine receptor in the IL interacted with an inhibitory guanyl nucleotide component (N_i) and that the stimulation of the D-2 dopamine receptor changed the properties of N_i so that N_i could interact with GTP and inhibit adenylate cyclase activity.

Seeman et al. [16] examined the dopamine hypothesis of schizophrenia by measuring the density of dopamine receptors in the postmortem brains of 81 control subjects and 59 schizophrenics from four different countries. They observed that the densities of dopamine receptors in the tissues from the schizophrenic patients had a bimodal distribution in the caudate nucleus, putamen, and nucleus accumbens. Further, they observed that the two modes had the same dissociation constant for the labeled ligand used, even though, almost all the patients had been medicated with neuroleptics. This suggested that the neuroleptic doses were similar for the two populations of schizophrenics and provided a direct evidence for two distinct categories of schizophrenia.

Dopaminergic inhibition of prolactin release from the anterior pituitary might be mediated via both the adenylate cyclase and Ca^{2+} mobilization/phosphoinositide pathways. Senogles et al. [17] partially purified the D2-dopamine receptor of the bovine anterior pituitary, by affinity chromatography on CMOS-Sepharose (immobilized carboxymethylmethoxymethylcellulose). Their experimental observations suggested that the D2-dopamine receptor copurified with a pertussis toxin-sensitive guanine nucleotide binding protein (N). Via several lines of evidence, they indicated that endogenous pituitary N protein was functionally coupled to the D2 receptor. Further results suggested that no and/or a form of N_i distinct from the Mr 41,000 pertussis toxin substrate (N_i) was the predominant N protein functionally coupled with the D2-dopamine receptor of anterior pituitary.

Bunzow et al. [18] took advantage of the expected nucleotide sequence similarities between the D1 and D2 subtypes of Dopamine receptors to isolate genes coding for new receptors. Using the hamster β_2 -adrenergic receptor gene as a hybridization probe they isolated related genes including a cDNA encoding the rat D2 dopamine receptor.

Grandy et al. [19] isolated a clone encoding a human D2 dopamine receptor from a pituitary cDNA library and sequenced. Their deduced protein sequence was found to be 96% identical with that of the cloned rat receptor with one major difference: the human receptor contained an additional 29 amino acids in its putative third cytoplasmic loop. Further, southern blotting demonstrated the presence of only one human D2 receptor gene.

Preliminary studies showed that the dopamine D₁ receptor was expressed in cerebral meningioma tissue. Schrell et al. [20] presented evidence that the iodinated dopamine D₁ antagonist [¹²⁵I]SCH-23982 bound to dopamine binding sites in 33 of the 45 human cerebral meningiomas examined for this. They observed that the dopamine D₂ receptor was not present in the 30 meningiomas examined for this. Their findings indicated that the dopamine D₁ receptor identified was expressed alone and was therefore regulated independent of a D₂ receptor in cerebral meningioma tissue.

Using the polymerase chain reaction, Carroll et al. [21] reported the presence of the messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) for the dopamine D₁ and D₂ receptors and the prolactin receptor in meningioma tissue specimens and cell cultures derived from meningioma tissue. Their results suggested the existence of active dopamine D₁ receptors in cerebral meningiomas.

Trott et al. [22] aimed to investigate the presence and implications of a mutated p53 protein and dopamine D₂ receptor in a representative series of meningiomas and to correlate these findings with age, gender, tumor grade, and recurrence. They immunohistochemically evaluated the tumor tissue samples of 157 patients diagnosed with meningioma (37 males and 120 females, mean age 53.6 ± 14.3 years) who underwent surgical resection between 2003 and 2012, for the presence of p53 protein and dopamine D₂ receptor and followed-up to analyze tumor recurrence or regrowth. They found 93.6% and 49.7% positive expression for Dopamine D₂ receptor and p53 protein, respectively. They hypothesized that the high positivity of dopamine D₂ receptor required further investigation of the therapeutic potential of dopamine agonists in the evolution of meningiomas.

In 2000, the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine was awarded to Arvid Carlsson, Department of Pharmacology, Göteborg University for the discovery that dopamine is a transmitter in the brain and that it has great importance for our ability to control movements, while Paul Greengard, Laboratory of Molecular and Cellular Science, Rockefeller University, New York, for the discovery of how dopamine and a number of other transmitters exert their action in the nervous system.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [23] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [24] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [24].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [25]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as

per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [26], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [23] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [23]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [27], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based

sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. DRD2 related synergies

Note - DRD2 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of DRD2 were recorded.

3.1.1. DRD2 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with DRD2 showed high rankings - prominin 1 (PROM1), flavin containing dimethylaniline monooxygenase 1 (FMO1), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), fibulin 1 (FBLN1), secreted frizzled related protein 4 (SFRP4), ST8 alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminide alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), proteoglycan 4 (PRG4), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), neutrophilin 2 (NXP2), fasciculation and elongation protein zeta 1 (FEZ1), mo-hawk homeobox (MKX), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), serine protease

23 (PRSS23), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), enkurin, TRPC channel interacting protein (ENKUR), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), thyroid hormone receptor beta (THRB), ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), VENT homeobox (VENTX), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), roundabout guidance receptor 3 (ROBO3), ABI family member 3 binding protein (ABI3BP), chromosome 10 open reading frame 90 (C10orf90), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), matrix metallopeptidase 16 (MMP16), tetraspanin 7 (TSPAN7), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1 (EXTL1), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), meiosis 1 associated protein (M1AP), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), ELAV like RNA binding protein 4 (ELAVL4), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4 / ODAD2), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), secretogranin II (SCG2), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14),

yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 3124 (C2orf27A / LINC03124), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase 27, atypical (DUSP27 / STYXL2), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A / NALF1), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of DRD2 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed

by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS DRD2									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T DRD2									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
PROM1 - DRD2	226	194	210	6	FMO1 - DRD2	185	176	209	366
SLC12A1 - DRD2	240	275	241	370	FBLN1 - DRD2	186	173	193	376
SFRP4 - DRD2	195	211	191	78	ST8SIA1 - DRD2	191	214	252	15
PRG4 - DRD2	188	133	202	357	TRIM67 - DRD2	203	188	205	8
LAMP5 - DRD2	237	248	306	51	LHCGR - DRD2	199	221	199	11
RBP4 - DRD2	239	212	215	158	FGF7 - DRD2	222	208	232	368
NXPH2 - DRD2	223	216	303	21	FEZ1 - DRD2	316	335	278	140
MKX - DRD2	309	251	286	88	ARID5B - DRD2	391	299	353	160
PRSS23 - DRD2	211	376	310	95	CRIM1 - DRD2	375	331	350	114
ENKUR - DRD2	322	315	325	126	KCNA6 - DRD2	217	213	227	385
THRB - DRD2	264	255	264	331	ADAMTS12 - DRD2	277	285	228	38
VENTX - DRD2	291	314	332	347	KCNE4 - DRD2	303	308	367	323
PID1 - DRD2	252	189	212	374	DDAH1 - DRD2	354	307	352	245
ROBO3 - DRD2	246	325	257	320	ABI3BP - DRD2	293	234	295	375
C10orf90 - DRD2	273	227	347	58	PDE1C - DRD2	263	223	180	381
MMP16 - DRD2	256	351	281	317	TSPAN7 - DRD2	335	339	305	303
PPP2R2B - DRD2	204	283	234	23	SUSD3 - DRD2	317	387	391	192
MYO1E - DRD2	363	371	339	130	EXTL1 - DRD2	238	303	307	346
SLAMF8 - DRD2	378	318	374	208	RUNX1 - DRD2	392	259	337	221
MIAP - DRD2	365	336	392	175	TCHH - DRD2	288	392	387	137
CHCHD6 - DRD2	295	354	386	222	COL26A1 - DRD2	228	229	217	4
SIGLEC11 - DRD2	381	321	372	254	SIGLEC16 - DRD2	310	356	384	266
LRP5 - DRD2	357	291	376	115	ELAVL4 - DRD2	281	375	368	209
MXRA8 - DRD2	279	348	266	230	VCAM1 - DRD2	328	217	283	122
NLRP3 - DRD2	340	309	341	241	CCDC74A - DRD2	385	324	320	143
C1QTNF7 - DRD2	215	215	268	12	NKX6-1 - DRD2	269	366	388	144
APBB2 - DRD2	343	357	381	223	HPGD - DRD2	301	293	309	73
F2RL2 - DRD2	254	305	334	355	RHOBTB3 - DRD2	265	210	237	386
EBF1 - DRD2	243	343	235	102	TMEM200A - DRD2	253	380	326	246
DACT2 - DRD2	235	300	292	75	MYOZ3 - DRD2	368	268	206	56
COL1A2 - DRD2	346	311	375	153	SBSPON - DRD2	306	222	276	378
TMEM71 - DRD2	345	329	390	127	SVEP1 - DRD2	271	258	249	28
HSPA12A - DRD2	260	280	298	343	PDZRN4 - DRD2	193	243	201	194
HTRA1 - DRD2	305	365	340	176	TMEM130 - DRD2	214	190	167	348
MFAP4 - DRD2	289	327	245	354	TVP23A - DRD2	349	361	327	138
NNMT - DRD2	219	242	223	17	LDHD - DRD2	307	370	282	277
PRRT2 - DRD2	348	334	317	267	CYP2S1 - DRD2	296	281	315	311
NT5DC2 - DRD2	355	349	389	224	FILIP1L - DRD2	383	377	336	216
RAB31 - DRD2	276	364	323	145	NPNT - DRD2	315	381	378	235
ATOX8 - DRD2	351	312	324	185	VAMP5 - DRD2	274	382	355	82
ENHO - DRD2	286	289	238	49	ARMC4 - DRD2	284	277	240	141
CPT1C - DRD2	347	238	222	33	CCDC126 - DRD2	379	363	285	268
STK32A - DRD2	249	244	248	29	GPR183 - DRD2	337	267	377	186
ITGAM - DRD2	338	287	345	312	GPR27 - DRD2	248	282	321	313

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between DRD2 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t DRD2 with DRD2 – > PROM1 / FMO1 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / SFRP4 / ST8SIA1 / PRG / TRIM67 / LAMP5 / LHCGR / RBP4 / FGF7 / NXPH2 / FEZ1 / MKX / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / ENKUR /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS DRD2									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T DRD2									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MAP6 - DRD2	360	273	354	124	SCG2 - DRD2	208	225	214	342
MACROD2 - DRD2	369	362	366	225	STAR5 - DRD2	372	284	255	261
IL17D - DRD2	359	350	300	187	PEAK1 - DRD2	285	292	383	316
SUSD5 - DRD2	255	341	239	334	HEG1 - DRD2	302	385	244	271
HOXB2 - DRD2	213	316	333	242	CD248 - DRD2	266	207	251	161
DNAH12 - DRD2	339	257	195	62	P2RY14 - DRD2	282	301	271	48
YPEL2 - DRD2	361	332	358	240	FAM131A - DRD2	356	319	361	77
CAPP4 - DRD2	342	372	363	298	SLCO3A1 - DRD2	234	272	314	359
BOK - DRD2	308	358	385	353	MAMSTR - DRD2	244	295	250	210
FZD8 - DRD2	330	374	267	162	MYOZ1 - DRD2	294	241	246	188
PDE4DIP - DRD2	364	390	294	236	CSRNP3 - DRD2	373	330	380	200
CIITA - DRD2	297	270	360	201	KCNE1 - DRD2	390	352	359	211
NME9 - DRD2	304	265	342	226	PLAG1 - DRD2	377	359	253	227
EXT1 - DRD2	319	391	329	255	BGN - DRD2	334	313	296	247
EPHB3 - DRD2	326	290	319	189	PLCB1 - DRD2	336	197	258	111
NTM - DRD2	224	206	273	40	RGS6 - DRD2	247	231	236	5
PAPPA - DRD2	231	239	259	9	PYCR1 - DRD2	321	288	369	146
NEB - DRD2	280	322	346	299	FAM43B - DRD2	292	260	344	150
TMEM119 - DRD2	268	228	233	66	OLFML1 - DRD2	261	337	247	256
DUSP5P1 - DRD2	232	346	288	272	ADRA2C - DRD2	366	278	287	105
PRKD1 - DRD2	387	389	382	257	CSF1 - DRD2	387	389	382	257
FLRT2 - DRD2	320	276	301	286	PRKG1 - DRD2	283	378	349	322
SHC4 - DRD2	257	263	265	309	CYP4Z1 - DRD2	352	333	365	291
CYP4X1 - DRD2	370	340	291	119	RTN4RL2 - DRD2	386	269	357	120
C2orf88 - DRD2	382	384	263	116	KBTBD12 - DRD2	331	342	311	292
LDLRAD2 - DRD2	259	247	280	52	ENTPD8 - DRD2	324	323	260	304
PLAC9 - DRD2	251	271	277	43	NUGGC - DRD2	300	235	330	45
FAM180A - DRD2	212	200	174	387	STK31 - DRD2	332	266	371	74
MME - DRD2	196	240	204	384	DACT3 - DRD2	367	286	373	305
ADARB1 - DRD2	350	306	269	202	SPN - DRD2	287	344	328	177
C2orf27A - DRD2	362	388	308	193	CLEC9A - DRD2	272	304	229	50
MT1F - DRD2	380	347	312	163	ITGBL1 - DRD2	388	373	322	190
MMP17 - DRD2	267	256	318	217	DLL1 - DRD2	311	296	313	310
ZNF521 - DRD2	241	226	225	37	RYR3 - DRD2	318	245	220	275
DUSP27 - DRD2	312	345	364	110	RNU6-529P - DRD2	299	369	348	278
RHOT1P2 - DRD2	205	224	203	7	PLPP4 - DRD2	242	246	302	53
SYT15 - DRD2	290	368	356	258	TMEM240 - DRD2	353	328	242	178
ANKRD20A9P - DRD2	182	187	211	383	HACD2 - DRD2	323	379	290	293
GPX3 - DRD2	218	253	261	249	HMGB3P7 - DRD2	374	252	343	41
ANKRD20A11P - DRD2	245	237	183	294	RFPL1S - DRD2	314	386	331	164
LINC00937 - DRD2	344	294	338	131	LINC01907 - DRD2	333	360	370	165
ITGB2-AS1 - DRD2	278	261	335	123	LMCD1-AS1 - DRD2	313	279	279	106
CYP4F29P - DRD2	229	219	213	389	ZNF883 - DRD2	325	326	379	203
SNX18P13 - DRD2	207	249	254	371					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between DRD2 VS Individual members.

KCNA6 / THRB / ADAMTS12 / VENTX / KCNE4 / PID1 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / PDE1C / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / SUSD3 / MYO1E / EXT1L1 / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / COL26A1 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / VCAM1 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A / C1QTNF7 / NKX6-1 / APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / TMEM200A / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / COL1A2 / SBSPON / TMEM71 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / HTRA1 / TMEM130 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / NNMT / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126

/ STK32A / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / SCG2 / MACROD2 / STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / SUSD5 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic DRD2 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of DRD2-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t DRD2

PROM1 / FMO1 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / SFRP4 ...

ST8SIA1 / PRG / TRIM67 / LAMP5 / LHCGR ...

RBP4 / FGF7 / NXPH2 / FEZ1 / MKX / ARID5B ...

PRSS23 / CRIM1 / ENKUR / KCNA6 / THRB ...

ADAMTS12 / VENTX / KCNE4 / PID1 / DDAH1 ...

ROBO3 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / PDE1C / MMP16 ...

TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / SUSD3 / MYO1E / EXTL1 ...

SLAMF8 / RUNX1/ M1AP/ TCHH/ CHCHD6/ COL26A1 ...

SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 ...

VCAM1 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A / C1QTNF7 / NKX6-1 ...

APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 ...

TMEM200A / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / COL1A2 / SBSPON ...

TMEM71 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / HTRA1 ...

TMEM130/ MFAP4/ TVP23A/ NNMT/ LDHD/ PRRT2 ...

CYP2S1/ NT5DC2/ FILIP1L/ RAB31/ NPNT/ ATOH8 ...

VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126 / STK32A ...

GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / SCG2 / MACROD2 ...

STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / SUSD5 / HEG1 / HOXB2 ...

CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 ...

SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP ...

CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN ...

EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 / NEB ...

FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C ...

PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 ...

CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 ...

ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / MME ...

DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / MT1F ...

ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 ...

RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / TMEM240 ...

ANKRD20A9P/ HACD2/ GPX3/ HMGB3P7/ ANKRD20A11P ...

RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 ...

LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P/ ZNF883/ SNX18P13 DRD2

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between DRD2 and Individual members.

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